

Assessing Gender Dynamics in Artisanal Fishing Communities in Delta State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated gender dynamics within artisanal fishing communities in Delta State, Nigeria. The study was guided by three research questions that addressed: the sources of information for fishermen/women, the level of involvement in fishing activities across different age and gender groups, and whether significant differences exist in involvement among these groups. The study targeted adults (ages 35 – 80), youths (ages 20-34), and children (ages 10-19) involved in artisanal fishing in Delta State, with a sample size of 151 respondents selected using a multi-stage sampling technique. Data was collected through structured questionnaires administered via interviews and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical tools, including frequencies, percentage distributions, and ANOVA. Findings revealed that the primary sources of information for fishing enterprise were relatives and radio, indicating a strong familial bond among respondents. Additionally, a high percentage of adult females, youth females, adult males, and children were frequently involved in fish catching, while adult males were more commonly engaged in loading, repairing canoes, packing fish, and servicing fishing gear. A significant difference in involvement across gender and age groups was observed, highlighting the prevalence of gender dynamics in artisanal fishing activities. In conclusion, the study emphasized the importance of addressing gender dynamics within artisanal fishing communities. It recommended the implementation of tailored community radio programmes by government agencies to enhance communication and knowledge-sharing among fishing communities.

Keywords: Assessing; Gender; Dynamics; Artisanal; Fishing Communities.

Introduction

Artisanal fishing communities represent a significant portion of the global fishing industry, often operating in coastal regions and relying on traditional methods passed down through generations. Gender dynamics within these communities play a pivotal role in shaping social, economic, and environmental aspects of their livelihoods. Artisanal fishing plays a significant role in the economy and culture of communities residing near water bodies in Delta State, Nigeria. With its diverse range of water sources, including rivers, lakes, streams, and coastal lagoons, the region supports a thriving fishing industry that provides sustenance and livelihoods for thousands of individuals. In Nigeria, fish occupies a crucial position as a primary source of animal protein, offering a cost-effective supplement to meat protein in the face of rising meat prices. According

to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), fish contributes significantly to animal intake (Atakpo, 2020), particularly in coastal and riverine communities, where it can constitute up to 80% of protein intake. Fishing activities, therefore, constitute the traditional occupation of communities residing near water bodies, including the River Niger and River Benue, which traverse the country.

Gender roles in artisanal fishing communities are deeply entrenched in cultural and historical contexts. The concept of gender, as defined by Pereira (2001) and the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), refers to socially constructed roles and relationships between men and women, shaped by social, political, and economic contexts rather than biology. These gender roles influence the division of labor within artisanal fishing communities, with men and women often assigned different tasks based on culturally prescribed norms and expectations.

Traditionally, fishing has been perceived as a predominantly male activity, with men responsible for offshore fishing activities, such as boat handling and net mending, while women primarily engage in onshore tasks like fish processing and marketing (Kleiber et al., 2015). However, recent studies have highlighted the significant contributions of women to the sector, challenging conventional gender norms and emphasizing the need for a more nuanced understanding of gender dynamics in fishing communities (Harper et al., 2018).

Economic pressures and environmental changes have led to shifts in gender roles within artisanal fishing communities. For instance, declining fish stocks and competition from industrial fishing operations have compelled men to seek alternative livelihoods, leaving women to assume greater responsibilities in fishing activities (Allison & Ellis, 2001). Moreover, the feminization of poverty has driven women to take on multiple roles, including income generation through fishing-related enterprises, thereby reshaping traditional gender divisions (Kleiber et al., 2015). These changes underscore the adaptive capacity of artisanal fishing communities in responding to external pressures while also highlighting the evolving nature of gender dynamics within these contexts.

Despite the significant contributions of women to artisanal fishing, they often face numerous challenges and inequalities compared to their male counterparts. Women frequently encounter barriers to accessing resources such as credit, technology, and training, limiting their participation and economic empowerment in the sector (Harper et al., 2018, (Atakpo, Obed-Chukwuka & Akpotu, 2024). Additionally, patriarchal structures and cultural norms may perpetuate gender-based discrimination and hinder women's decision-making authority within fishing communities (Kleiber et al., 2015). Addressing these inequalities is imperative for

promoting inclusive and sustainable development in artisanal fishing communities and harnessing the full potential of both men and women in the sector.

Research Questions

1. What are the sources of information for fishermen/women in the study area?
2. What is the level of involvement on fishing production activities among adult males, adult females, youth males, youth females and children in the study area?
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of involvement in fishing activities between adult male, adult female, youth male, youth female and children's respondents?

Theoretical Framework

This study is based on the theory of social roles that explain the roles of gender in fishing activities. According to this theory, behavioural sex differences spring from the different social roles inhabited by women and men, especially those concerning the division of labour (Eagly et al., 2000). Historically, men and women are assigned to labour in task that are consistent with their physical attributes, as a result of economic, ecological, social and technological pressures they are being exposed to. Thus, men were more likely to fulfil task that require speed, strength and ability to be away from home for expanded period of times. Conversely, because women were primarily responsible for child bearing, they are more likely to fulfil task related to home and family as a result of the different social roles inhabited by men and women. Base on this division of labour, gender roles developed concerning expectation about the characteristics and behaviours of women and men, thus men are expected to fulfil the masculine gender roles that reflect ingenuity qualities and women are expected to fulfil the feminine gender roles that reflect communal qualities (Wood & Eagly, 2002).

Literature Review

In Nigeria women are deeply involved in artisanal fisheries activities including unloading of fish from landing canoes, fish processing and fish marketing that form the link between production and consumption (Adedokun, 2000). Women constitute about half of the population actively involved in fisheries development project and programmes (Faturoti, 1999). However, fisheries development project and programmes are often biased towards men and the involvement in planning and programming is very limited. Furthermore, fisheries policy and programmes addressing the specific issue of women are virtually no existent. The educational status of women in the fisheries sector compared to men is inferior and women do not have special programmes for their training in technological improvement (Adekanye, 2004), they also do not have access to

credit and finances and enjoy limited attention in terms of expansion of their activities. Moreover, women are not fully involved in decision making process and their level of organization and response to their needs are limited. Hence the emancipation of women in the fisheries sector in terms of freely expressing their needs and aspiration and effectively shaping their future is yet to be realized (Boserup, 1970).

Despite their level of involvement in activities of the sector, women operations are often small scale and their income is small compared to their male counterparts. They face challenges including inadequate market and transportation problems. They do not have access to distant markets. This is because they are not allowed by their husbands to trade their products; hence they lag behind in the equitable distribution of incomes (Adedokun, 2000).

Fisheries and aquaculture value chains are diverse and often complex and dynamic systems, with men and women often undertaking different and changing roles depending on local norms about resource access and control and mobility, type of technology involved, the extent of commercialization, and the product involved. Many small-scale fisheries operate with the men investing in fishing vessels, nets, and other gear and doing the fishing and with the women investing in processing equipment and being responsible for fish purchasing, processing, and sales, but this pattern is not followed everywhere. In terms of boat investments, in some situations women use the proceeds from their trading to invest in boats and gear (Walker, 2001). These women may not enter the water to fish but may hire crews for their own boats, thus securing their incomes from fresh or processed fish. Women collect shellfish, including crabs, and produce shellfish seed. Women's involvement in fish processing is widespread and, along with the collection activities described here, is regarded as an appropriate activity for women given their domestic tasks and responsibilities. In small-scale systems, although it is possible to detail the divisions of labour by sex, often whole families are involved. Therefore, even though it is largely men who fish and women who purchase the fish, the women may include wives and other women relatives, especially those who have helped the fisher in the past and traders who have provided credit, who may also be relatives. Jul-Larsen et al., (2003) describe the multiplicity and complexity of the relationships that men fishers working on Lake Victoria have with their women buyers and how these relationships influence how much fish they are allowed to buy. Consequently, even if one sex faces greater business risks than the other, without detailed, context-specific intra-household information on roles and responsibilities, it is difficult to predict the impact on household livelihoods. Regardless of gender-role differences, wealthier groups of women and men

play dominant roles in the parts of the chains where they operate. Poor members of the chain have weak bargaining power and little control over others in the chain and prices paid for goods and services, and they are more vulnerable than healthier groups to decreases in catch and poor services because they are unable to accumulate assets. For example, in capture fisheries not all men own boats. The majority work as crew and may never accumulate enough assets to own a boat (Allison, 2003). The same is true of processors and traders. In parts of West Africa a hierarchy of traders and processors exist, with younger and poorer women working for wealthier ones and depending on them for their livelihoods. The situation of these poorer women involved in fish processing is demonstrated in the following description from the Sustainable Fisheries Livelihoods Programme (SFLP, 2006) of women fish processors in West Africa: Their activities are less profitable; they access poor quality fish and are unable to keep fish fresh thereby attracting higher prices, since they have no information on marketing or ice. Loans from micro-finance institutions serve more as revolving funds for marketing than investment loans for fishing and processing equipment. Informal and formal credit is risky because profits are minimal. Poorer women use revolving funds to meet household expenses in periods of poor catch which reduces funds available for business. Most female-owned fishery enterprises are therefore small, and grow slowly, if at all (Benin, Niger and The Gambia in West Africa).

Understanding the sources of information for fishermen and women is crucial for effective fisheries management and community development initiatives. These sources play a pivotal role in shaping fishing practices, decision-making processes, and access to resources within fishing communities. One important source of information is radio broadcasts, which often disseminate news, weather forecasts, market prices, and extension services tailored to the needs of fishers. Radio programs dedicated to fisheries provide timely updates on fishing regulations, safety guidelines, and market opportunities, reaching remote and marginalized fishing communities that may have limited access to other forms of communication (Belhabib et al., 2019). By leveraging the widespread availability of radio receivers, broadcasters can effectively engage fishers and disseminate valuable information to support their livelihoods and enhance their resilience to environmental and socio-economic challenges.

Television programs also serve as a significant source of information for fishermen and women, offering visual content on fishing techniques, gear innovations, and sustainable practices. Fisheries-related documentaries, educational videos, and reality shows provide opportunities for knowledge exchange, skill development, and awareness-raising campaigns on topics such as

marine conservation, fisheries management, and occupational health and safety (Adams et al., 2016). Moreover, television advertisements and infomercials promote fishing gear, equipment, and services, influencing fishers' purchasing decisions and technological adoption patterns (Mahanty et al., 2018). By harnessing the power of visual media, broadcasters can engage fishers across different age groups and literacy levels, fostering learning and behavior change within fishing communities.

Community meetings and gatherings serve as vital forums for information exchange, knowledge sharing, and collective decision-making among fishermen and women. These gatherings provide opportunities for fishers to discuss local issues, voice concerns, and negotiate access to fishing grounds and resources (Frangoudes et al., 2016). Extension agents, government officials, and community leaders often facilitate these meetings, providing technical assistance, legal advice, and support services to empower fishers and strengthen community cohesion (Jentoft et al., 2003). By fostering dialogue and collaboration, community meetings enable fishers to collectively address common challenges, such as overfishing, habitat degradation, and conflicts over resource use, leading to more sustainable and equitable fisheries management outcomes.

Relatives and social networks also play a significant role in shaping fishers' access to information, resources, and opportunities within fishing communities. Family members, friends, and neighbors often share knowledge, skills, and experiences related to fishing practices, local conditions, and market dynamics (Coulthard et al., 2011). Interactions within social networks facilitate informal learning, mentorship, and knowledge transfer between generations, ensuring the continuity of traditional fishing knowledge and adaptive strategies (Béné et al., 2010). Moreover, social ties provide emotional support, solidarity, and mutual aid during times of crisis or hardship, strengthening the social fabric of fishing communities and enhancing their resilience to external shocks (Cinner et al., 2018).

Fisherfolk organizations and cooperatives serve as important channels for information dissemination, advocacy, and collective action among fishermen and women. These grassroots organizations represent the interests of fishers, mobilize community resources, and engage in participatory decision-making processes at local, regional, and national levels (Bavinck et al., 2015). Through newsletters, workshops, and training programs, fisher-folk organizations provide members with updates on policy developments, market trends, and technical innovations, empowering them to make informed choices and navigate changing socio-economic landscapes (Campling et al., 2015). By promoting solidarity, self-reliance, and empowerment, fisher-folk

organizations contribute to the socio-economic development and political empowerment of fishing communities, fostering greater resilience and sustainability in the face of external pressures and uncertainties.

Study Area

The study area is Delta State which is located in the Niger Delta Basin of the country with longitude 5°00 and 6° 45'E and latitude 5°00 and 6°30'N. It has a landmass of 18,050 square kilometres (6,833 sq mi) with three senatorial districts (Delta North, Delta South, and Delta Central). Delta North comprises of nine (9) local government areas, Delta South consist of eight (8) local government areas, while Delta central is made up of eight (8) local government areas, which makes up the twenty five local government areas in Delta state. The state has a population of 4,098,391 (NPC, 2006) out of which 2,024,085 are female of which 1,032,013 are farmers (FRN, 2007). The traditional occupations of the people include farming, fishing and retail trading with abundant mineral resources of crude oil and gas, almost all year round rainfall, fresh water sources and forest resources. The present of mineral resources has made the state to be strategic to the economy of Nigeria.

Methodology

The study's population included adults (ages 35 – 80), youth (ages 20-34), and children (ages 10-19) in Delta State, encompassing both males and females. The respondents were selected using a multi-stage sampling technique. Initially, six out of the twenty-five Local Government Areas (LGAs) in Delta State were purposively chosen due to their involvement in artisanal fishing. From these six LGAs, two were randomly selected, namely Warri North and Burutu, each with five fishing communities. One fishing community from each of the two selected LGAs was then randomly chosen, totaling two communities (Ayakoromo and Koko). A sample frame was generated for each category (old male, old female, youth male, youth female, and children) across gender and generation using snowballing within the communities. Simple random sampling was then used to select 5% of respondents from each community, resulting in a total of 151 respondents.

Structured questionnaires were administered through interview schedules to collect quantitative data from the respondents. The instrument underwent content and face validity testing with assistance from experts in the Department of Agricultural Extension and Rural Development at the University of Ibadan. The reliability of the instrument was determined using the split-half method. The collected data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical tools such as frequencies, percentage distributions, and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

Results

RQ 1: What are the sources of information for fishermen/women in the study area?

Table 1: Frequency distribution of respondents' Use of source of information

Use of sources of information	A M F %	A F F %	Y M F %	Y F F %	Children F %	Total
Radio						
Never	5 18.5%	13 31.7%	5 38.5%	7 18.4%	15 46.9%	45 29.8%
Occasionally	10 37.0%	7 17.1%	6 46.2%	17 44.7%	4 12.5%	44 29.1%
Regularly	12 44.4%	21 51.2%	2 15.4%	14 36.8%	13 40.6%	62 41.1%
Television						
Never	20 74.1%	37 90.2%	10 76.9%	34 89.5%	31 96.9%	132 87.4%
Occasionally	3 11.1%	4 9.8%	2 15.4%	1 2.6%	1 3.1%	11 7.3%
Regularly	4 14.8%	0 0	1 7.7%	3 7.9%	0 0	8 5.3%
Relatives						
Never	1 3.7%	6 14.6%	3 23.1%	4 10.5%	11 34.4%	25 16.6%
Occasionally	8 29.6%	6 14.6%	6 46.2%	10 26.3%	4 12.5%	34 22.5%
Regularly	18 66.7%	29 70.7%	4 30.8%	24 63.2%	17 53.1%	92 60.9%
Extension agent.						
Never	27 100%	41 100%	13 100%	38 100%	32 100%	151 100%
Print media						
Never	26 96.3%	41 27.2%	12 92.3%	38 100%	32 100%	149 98.7%
Occasionally	1 3.7%	0 0	1 7.7%	0 0	0 0	2 1.3%
Monthly meeting						
Never	25 92.6%	41 27.2%	12 92.3%	38 100%	32 100%	148 98%
Occasionally	2 7.4%	0 0	1 7.7%	0 0	0 0	3 2.0%
Social group						
Never	26 96.3%	39 95.1%	12 92.3%	38 100%	32 100%	147 97.4%
Occasionally	1 3.7%	2 4.9%	0 0	0 0	0 0	3 2.0%
Regularly	0 0	0 0	1 7.7%	0 0	0 0	1 0.7%
Fisher-folks						
Never	24 88.9%	40 97.6%	12 92.3%	38 100%	32 100%	146 96.7%
Sometimes	2 7.4%	0 0	1 7.7%	0 0	0 0	3 2.0%
Regularly	1 0.7%	1 2.4%	0 0	0 0	0 0	2 1.3%
Fish marketers						
Never	15 55.6%	32 78.0%	8 61.5%	27 71.1%	32 100%	114 75.5%
Sometimes	6 22.2%	3 7.3%	4 30.8%	10 26.3%	0 0	23 15.2%
Regularly	6 22.2%	6 14.6%	1 7.7%	1 2.6%	0 0	14 9.3%

Data analysis (2014)

AM=Adult male, AF=Adult female, YM=Youth male, YF=Youth female

The results on Table 1 show that information on fishing enterprise is majorly received through relatives and radio. As 60.9% and 22.5% of the respondents used it regularly and occasionally respectively, radio usage was 41.1% and 29.1% regularly and occasionally. Information through

extension agent was 100% never as extension services are not available in the study area also the use of print media is almost non-existence despite their educational attainment. This suggests a strong family bond among respondents.

RQ 2: What is the level of involvement on fishing production activities among adult males, adult females, youth males, youth females and children in the study area?

Table 2: Frequency distribution involvement in fish production activities by respondents

Fishing production activities	Adult male		Adult female		Youth male		Youth Female		Children		Total	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Fish catching												
Not involved	1	3.7	1	2.4	0	0	0	0	1	3.1	3	2.0
Rarely involved	1	3.7	0	0	4	30.8	0	0	5	15.6	10	6.6
Often involved	25	92.6	40	97.6	9	69.2	38	100	26	81.3	138	91.4
Harvesting												
Not involved	2	7.4	1	2.4	1	7.7	1	2.6	2	6.3	7	4.6
Rarely involved	1	3.7	0	0	3	23.1	0	0	5	15.6	9	6.0
Often involved	24	88.9	40	97.6	9	69.2	37	97.4	25	78.1	135	89.4
Procurement of equipment												
Not involved	0	0	0	0	1	7.7	2	5.3	10	31.3	13	8.6
Rarely involved	19	70.4	40	97.6	12	92.3	34	89.5	22	68.8	127	84.1
Often involved	8	29.6	1	2.4	0	0	2	5.3	0	0	11	7.3
Mending of fish nets												
Not involved	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	31.3	10	3.3
Rarely involved	22	81.5	40	97.6	12	92.3	38	100	22	68.8	134	88.7
Often involved	5	18.5	1	2.4	1	7.7	0	0	0	0	7	4.6
Repairing of canoe												
Not involved	1	3.7	37	90.2	0	0	22	57.9	29	90.6	89	58.9
Rarely involved	22	81.5	4	9.8	13	100	16	42.1	3	9.4	58	38.4
Often involved	4	14.8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	2.6
Loading of fish												
Not involved	5	18.5	8	19.5	3	23.1	8	21.1	23	71.9	47	31.1
Rarely involved	3	11.1	9	22	4	30.8	7	18.4	2	6.3	25	16.6
Often involved	19	70.4	24	58.5	6	46.2	23	60.5	7	21.9	79	52.3
Packaging of fish for easy												
Not involved	6	22.2	6	14.6	3	23.1	8	21.1	25	78.1	48	31.8
Rarely involved	3	11.1	9	22	4	30.8	7	18.4	1	3.1	24	15.9
Often involved	18	66.7	26	63	6	46.2	23	60.5	6	18.8	79	52.3
Servicing of motorized gears												
Not involved	20	74.1	38	92.7	9	69.2	35	92.1	31	96.9	133	88.1
Rarely involved	5	18.5	3	7.3	4	30.8	3	7.9	1	3.1	16	10.6
Often involved	2	7.4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1.3

Data analysis (2014)

Data in Table 2 show that 97.6% of adult female, 100% of youth female, 92.6% of adult female, 81.3% of children and 69.2% of youth male are often involved in fish catching. Majority of respondents are rarely involved in mending of fishing nets (88.7%) and procurement of fishing

equipment (84.3%) while majority of the respondents are not involved in repairing of canoe (58.3) and Servicing of motorized gears (88.1%). Also more adult males are often involved in loading of fishing, repairing of canoe, packing of fish for transport and servicing of fishing gears. Male fisher-folks are more likely to use the modern (motorized) fishing machines than the risk- adverse female counterparts, while more adult females and youth females are involved in fish catching and harvesting. This implies that there is difference in fish production activities involved in across gender.

RQ 3: Is there a significant difference in the level of involvement in fishing activities between adult male, adult female, youth male, youth female and children respondents?

Table 3: ANOVA of involvement in fishing of adult male, adult female, youth male, youth female and children

Variable	DF	Mean square	p-value	F
Level of involvement in fishing activities	3	3.116	0.000 [*]	18.528

Data analysis (2014)

Involvement level

Duncan (a,b)	Gender	N	Subset for the alpha 0.5		
	Children	32	1.0938 ^c		
	youth female	38		1.5000 ^b	
	youth male	13		1.5385 ^b	
	adult female	41			1.8049 ^a
	adult male	27			1.8889 ^a
	Sig.		1.000	0.738	0.465

Source: Data Analysis (2014)

***significant@ p≤0.05**

Table 3 show that there is significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$, $F=18.528$) between the level of adult male, adult female, youth male, youth female, children and their involvement in fishing activities with a mean square difference of 3.116. This implies that the involvement of respondents in fishing activities is strongly determined by their gender and generation. Further analysis by Duncan shows that the difference lies across their generation.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from Table 1 indicate that the primary sources of information for fishing enterprise among respondents in the study area are relatives and radio. A significant majority of respondents (60.9%) reported regularly receiving information through relatives, highlighting the importance of familial networks in transmitting knowledge and skills related to fishing activities. Additionally, radio emerged as another key source of information, with 41.1% of respondents

using it regularly. These findings suggest a strong family bond among respondents, as evidenced by the reliance on relatives for information dissemination. This finding is consistent with studies emphasizing the pivotal role of social networks and intergenerational knowledge transfer in small-scale fishing communities (e.g., Neis et al., 2005).

Moreover, the absence of extension services in the study area, indicated by 100% of respondents reporting never receiving information from extension agents, underscores the limited availability of formal support systems for fishers. This finding contrasts with findings from other works highlighting the importance of extension services in providing technical assistance, training, and access to resources for sustainable fisheries management (e.g., Salas et al., 2007). Additionally, the low utilization of print media despite respondents' educational attainment suggests potential gaps in communication channels for disseminating information on fishing practices and regulations.

In Table 2, the data reveal significant gender and generational differences in the types of fishing activities in which respondents are involved. Adult females and youth females are more likely to be involved in fish catching and harvesting, while adult males are more commonly engaged in tasks such as loading of fishing, repairing of canoes, packing of fish for transport, and servicing of fishing gears. These findings align with studies indicating gendered divisions of labor in artisanal fishing communities, where men typically engage in more physically demanding and risk-prone activities, while women focus on tasks closer to shore (e.g., Adeokun, 2000).

Furthermore, Table 3 demonstrates a significant difference in the involvement of respondents in fishing activities across gender and generation. The mean square difference of 3.116 suggests that gender and generation strongly determine the level of involvement in fishing activities. Further analysis using Duncan's test reveals differences across generations, indicating that fishing roles and responsibilities may evolve over time within fishing communities. These findings contribute to our understanding of the nuanced interplay of gender participation in fishing activities, highlighting the need for targeted interventions that recognize and address these dynamics to promote gender equality and sustainable livelihoods in artisanal fishing communities.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study sheds light on the intricate dynamics of information dissemination and participation in fishing activities within artisanal fishing communities. The reliance on relatives and radio for information underscores the significance of familial networks and

traditional communication channels in transmitting knowledge and skills related to fishing enterprise. However, the absence of extension services highlights the limited access to formal support systems, posing challenges for sustainable fisheries management. Furthermore, gender and differences in fishing activities reflect the gendered divisions of labor and evolving roles within fishing communities, emphasizing the importance of targeted interventions to promote gender equality and livelihood sustainability. Overall, these findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the socio-cultural and institutional factors shaping fishing practices, calling for holistic approaches that address the diverse needs and realities of artisanal fishing communities.

Recommendations

To address the identified issues, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Government agencies should implement customized community radio programs to improve communication among fishing communities. These programs should focus on sharing important information about fishing practices, market trends, and regulatory updates. By utilizing existing social networks, such as family and community ties, fishers can enhance their knowledge and skills through effective information dissemination both within and between communities.
2. Governmental agencies should expand support systems for fishers due to the absence of extension services. Establish local extension offices or outreach programs to provide technical assistance, training, and resources for sustainable fisheries management. Foster collaborative partnerships among government agencies, NGOs, and community-based organizations to deliver customized extension services tailored to the unique needs of artisanal fishing communities.
3. Diversify communication channels to overcome underutilization of print media. Utilize digital platforms such as mobile applications and social media to engage younger generations. Distribute traditional printed materials like pamphlets and posters through community centers and fishing cooperatives to complement existing communication efforts.
4. Prioritize gender equality and women's empowerment in fisheries management. Promote women's involvement in non-traditional fishing activities and provide capacity-building programs and leadership training to enhance their skills and representation in decision-making processes.

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